

Business Educators' Awareness of Technology Enhanced Resources for Teaching and Learning in Colleges of Education in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research study aims to investigate the level of awareness of technology-enhanced resources among business educators in colleges of education in Delta State, Nigeria. To accomplish this, three research questions were formulated and answered, while three corresponding hypotheses guided the study were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study, and the target population was 75 business educators in Delta State Colleges of Education. All 75 Business educators constitute the sample size since the total population is of manageable size. An instrument titled "Awareness of Technology-Enhanced Resources among Business Educators (ATERBEQ), validated by a business education expert was employed for data gathering. The correlation coefficient of the instrument was 0.80. The results showed that business educators in Delta States are highly aware of technology-enhanced teaching resources for their academic activities. Moreover, there was no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing TERs among business education lecturers at Delta State College of Education. The study also found a moderate positive and statistically significant relationship between teaching experience and usage of TERs among business educators. The study suggests, among other things, that colleges of education should encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing between business educators in Delta State to enhance the effective use of technology-enhanced teaching methods collectively.

Keyword: Awareness, Business Educators, Technology Enhance Resources (TERs), Teaching, College of Education

Introduction

The integration of technology in education is a crucial element of modern-day learning. It enhances traditional teaching methods, making education more engaging, effective, and accessible, Smith, and Johnson, (2021). Therefore, it is fundamental to understand how aware and accepting educators are of technology-enhanced teaching resources. In business education, technological integration is crucial to prepare students for a constantly changing and technology-based workforce by providing them with the necessary skills and knowledge. However, many business educators are unsure of how to integrate technology into their instructional delivery. Liadi, Adedapo, and Ibrahim, (2022), and therefore, it is vital to investigate the extent to which they use technology-enhanced teaching resources.

Technology Enhanced Resources (TERs) are modern tools that support, enhance, and even transform teaching practices both inside and outside the classroom, Liadi, and Bolupe, (2021). They include digital technologies such as web-based applications, computer devices, and online teaching, among others. TERs facilitate and enhance student learning in the classroom. Technology-enhanced resources can have a significant impact on the work of business educators. They provide a wide range of benefits such as easy access to information, increased student interest in learning, better retention of information, and improved presentation of information. Additionally, TERs facilitate interactive teaching and make knowledge sharing easier. Before requiring the use of TERs, business educators need to be aware of their existence. Awareness leads to a shift in teaching behavior and helps develop positive attitudes toward instructional technologies. It is important to consider whether business educators are aware of its existence.

Awareness refers to the ability to perceive, feel, or be conscious of events, objects, thoughts, emotions, or sensory patterns. It also involves knowing specific information that can be demonstrated through particular behavior (Akpojotor, 2016).

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Similarly, Oni and Ahiauzu (2016) also indicated that 'Awareness' is knowledge about something that exists or understanding of a situation or subject at present based on information or experience. In the context of this paper, awareness of TERs by business educators means having knowledge of the existing TERs opportunities and utilizing them to enhance effective and efficient instructional delivery. Whereas experience plays a pivotal role in the adoption of technology, Experience is the amount of time an individual spends being involved in something. According to a study by Kehinde, Aderibigbe, and Evans (2019) on the adoption of health information technology among healthcare workers in Thailand, experience has a moderating effect on the behavioral intention to use the technology, which implies that Business educators may intend to use TERs in their teaching if they have prior knowledge of technology adoption (Sadi & Haruna, 2020).

Therefore, it is crucial to investigate the level of awareness of TERs among business educators in Colleges of Education. Colleges of Education play an essential role in providing a strong foundation for teacher training and professional development. Business educators within these colleges have a significant impact on shaping the future of education in Nigeria. However, their effectiveness is dependent on their ability to embrace and leverage technology. Understanding the current level of awareness and adoption of technology-enhanced teaching resources among business educators in Delta State is essential to inform educational policies and practices.

Statement of the Research Problem

Business educators play a critical role in shaping the knowledge and skills of future professionals and leaders. While there is a growing trend towards digital learning environments and the potential for technology to enhance pedagogy, many academic institutions in Nigeria lack the necessary resources to incorporate ICT into their teaching practices Liadi (2015). As a result, the Federal Ministry of Education launched an ICT-driven project called "School Net" (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013) to provide computers to all schools in Nigeria to help them become more proficient in communication. However, many academic institutions in the country lack the requirements to use ICT in their teaching practices, Liadi (2015). As a result, they are unable to make an impact on teaching methods across the nation, and there remains a significant gap in the utilization of technology-enhanced resources among business educators in the Colleges of Education in Delta State, Nigeria. Onasanya (2010). The limited awareness and utilization of technology tools and resources for teaching may hinder the effective integration of innovative teaching methodologies, potentially hindering the enhancement of student's learning experience and the development of essential digital competencies (Sadi & Haruna, 2020). However, research has shown that business educators' preparedness to harness technology-enhanced resources in the teaching and learning process effectively remains underexplored (Egbri, 2010). There seem to be disparities in access to technology-enhanced teaching resources among business educators in Delta State. The level of awareness can inform the development of targeted professional development programs that cater to the specific needs and gaps in business educators' technological competencies. Therefore, it is empirically essential to investigate business educators' awareness of technology-enhanced resources for teaching in Delta State Colleges of Education.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate business educators' awareness of technology-enhanced resources for teaching in Delta State Colleges of Education. Specifically, the study investigated:

1. the level of awareness of business educators about technology-enhance teaching resources and teaching experience in the College of Education in Delta State.
2. the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among business educators in Delta State
3. the difference in the adoption and awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources between business educators in Delta State.

Research Questions.

1. What is the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business educators in the College of Education in Delta State?
2. What is the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources among business educators in Delta State?
3. What is the difference in the adoption and awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources between business educators in Colleges of Education in Delta State?

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Hypotheses

1. There is no significant correlation between the teaching experience of Business educators and their usage of technology-enhanced teaching resources.
2. There is no significant difference between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.
3. There is no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources among business education Lecturer in Delta State Colleges of Education,

Methodology

This study investigates the level of awareness of technology-enhanced resources among business educators in Delta State, a descriptive survey research design adopted for the study. The sample of the study was taken from a census of lecturers in two colleges of education that offer business education programs, resulting in a total of 75 lecturers from Federal Colleges of Education (Technical) Asaba, and College of Education, Agbor. To collect data, a structured questionnaire called "Awareness of Technology-Enhanced Resources among Business Educators (ATERBEQ)" was used. It consisted of two sections: Section A gathered demographic variables of the respondents, such as institution/colleges and working experience, while Section B contained 21 statements related to applying technology-enhanced resources (TERs) that were structured on a 5-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by experts in the field of Business Education and one expert in Educational Foundations (Evaluation and Measurement unit). The instrument was administered to 20 business educators of the Department of Business Education, Osun State College of Education, Ilesa, who were not part of the final study but had the same parameters as the colleges of study. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's alpha statistic, which yielded a value of $r=0.80$.

The researcher personally administered copies of the questionnaire to the respondents, with the help of two research assistants. Out of 85 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 75 were retrieved and used for data analysis. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, and the t-test and correlation analysis were used to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. If the p-value was less than the alpha value of 0.05, the hypothesis was rejected, but if it was greater or equal to the alpha value, the hypothesis was accepted.

Presentation of Results and Discussion

Research Question One: What is the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business educators in the College of Education in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean, and Standard Deviation on the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching Resources and teaching experience. (N =75)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	I am aware that there are numerous technology-enhanced teaching resources accessible to educators.	3.43	.72	Agreed
2.	I keep up to date with recent technological tools to enhance my teaching.	3.29	.59	Agreed
3.	I am well-versed in the advantages of using technology in the classroom.	3.11	.76	Agreed
4.	I make a conscious effort to pursue training and professional development opportunities that are relevant to the utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources.	3.43	.72	Agreed
5.	I am confident in my ability to incorporate technology into teaching.	3.40	.66	Agreed
6.	I use technology-enhanced teaching resources, such as e-learning platforms and multimedia, in my teaching.	3.11	.76	Agreed
7.	I believe that technology-enhanced teaching resources can enhance the educational experience for students.	3.40	.66	Agreed
Aggregate		3.31	0.70	Agreed

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Note. SD = standard deviation

The data presented in Table 1 depicts the level of awareness of technology-enhanced resources (TERs) for teaching among business educators in colleges of education located in Delta State. The responses indicate that the mean level of awareness of TERs varied from 3.11 to 3.43 with standard deviation values varying from 0.66 to 0.76. The overall mean and standard deviation were calculated to be 3.31 and 0.70, respectively. All measures had a standard deviation below one, which indicates that the awareness level of TERs exceeds the set criterion aggregate mean score of 3.00 for high extents. Thus, it can be concluded that business educators in Delta States are highly aware of technology-enhanced teaching resources for their teaching experience.

Research Question Two: What is the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources among business educators in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the extent of TERs utilization by business educators in their instructional practices (N =75)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
8.	How frequently do you integrate technology-enhanced teaching resources, such as multimedia presentations or online platforms, into your lessons?	3.43	.72	VF
9.	How often do you use e-learning platforms or digital resources for assignments, quizzes, or assessments in your courses?	3.36	.63	VF
10.	How frequently do you incorporate interactive technologies, such as educational apps or online simulations, in your teaching to enhance student engagement?	2.92	.71	VF
11.	How often do you encourage your students to use online research and resources as part of their assignments or projects?	3.01	.76	VF
12.	How frequently do you conduct virtual discussions or online forums to facilitate peer interaction and collaborative learning?	3.40	.66	VF
13.	How often do you employ technology-enhanced teaching resources to provide personalized feedback to your students, such as through online grading and feedback systems?	2.92	.75	VF
14.	How often do you participate in online professional communities, webinars, or conferences to stay updated on innovative teaching resources and methods?	2.88	.73	VF
Aggregate		3.13	0.71	VF

Note. SD = standard deviation VF = Very Frequent

Table 2 revealed data on the extent to which business educators in Delta States utilize technology-enhanced teaching resources in their instructional practices. The mean responses on the frequency of utilizing TERs varied from 2.88 to 3.43, with standard deviation values varying from .66 to .76. The aggregate mean and standard deviation were 3.13 and .71, separately. All measures had a standard deviation below one (1), indicating that business educators frequently utilized TERs in their instructional practices. This suggests that business educators in Delta States are very frequent in the utilization of TERs in their instructional practice.

Research Question Three: What is the difference in the adoption and awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources between business educators in Colleges of Education in Delta State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on the differences in awareness and utilization of TERs for teaching (N =75)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
15.	I believe that business educators in Delta State possess the same level of awareness of technology-enhanced resources for teaching.	3.43	.72	Agreed

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S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
16.	I believe that business educators at Delta State are more proactive in utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources in their teaching.	3.40	.66	Agreed
17.	There is no significant difference in the level of technological infrastructure and support available to educators in Delta State.	3.11	.76	Agreed
18.	Educational policies and initiatives in Delta State are more conducive to the adoption of technology-enhanced resources for teaching.	3.43	.72	Agreed
19.	The perceived level of institutional leadership support for technology integration in Delta State is the same.	3.37	.67	Agreed
20.	Business educators in Delta State have similar access to training and professional development opportunities related to technology-enhanced resources for teaching.	2.93	.70	Agreed
21.	A significant difference exists in the cultural or socio-economic factors that may impact the utilization of technology-enhanced teaching resources between Delta State.	3.03	.73	Agreed
Aggregate		3.24	0.71	Agreed

Note. SD = standard deviation

Table 3 presents data on the differences in awareness and utilization of technology-enhanced resources (TERs) among business educators in Delta States. The mean responses on the awareness and utilization of TERs varied from 2.93 to 3.43, with standard deviation values varying from 0.66 to 0.73. The aggregate mean and standard deviation were 3.24 and 0.71, respectively. All measures had a standard deviation below 1, indicating no significant differences in the responses on awareness and utilization of TERs for teaching. Therefore, it can be inferred that there is no distinction in awareness and adoption of TERs between business educators in Delta State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant correlation between the teaching experience of Business educators and their usage of technology-enhanced teaching resources.

Table 4: Correlation between the teaching experience of Business educators and their usage of TERs for teaching.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	R	P
Working Experience	75	1.5200	.50296	.313**	.006
TERs Utilization	75	22.6933	2.74587		

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

		Teaching Experience	TERs Utilization
Teaching Experience	Pearson Correlation	1	.313**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.006
	N	75	75
TERs Utilization	Pearson Correlation	.313**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	
	N	75	75

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 demonstrates the result of the Pearson product-moment correlation analysis between the teaching experience of business educators and their usage of TERs for teaching. The analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation that was statistically significant. Specifically, the correlation table indicated that there was a Moderate positive and statistically

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significant relationship between teaching experience and usage of TER among business educators at a 0.05 level of significance ($r = 313^{**}$, $p < 0.05$).

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Table 5: The t-test difference in the level of awareness of TERs and Teaching Experience.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p	Decision
Level of Awareness	75	23.1600	2.80463	74	70.610	.000	Significant
Teaching Experience	75	1.5200	.50296				

Note. SD = standard deviation.

In Table 5, the mean responses of Delta business educators were compared between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources (TERs) and the Teaching Experience. The results showed that the Level of awareness had a higher mean response ($M = 23.16$) than the Teaching experience ($M = 1.52$), with a mean difference of 21.64. However, since both mean scores were significantly different from the aggregate mean, the responses indicated differences in the level of awareness of TERs for teaching and teaching experience. The table also revealed that there was no notable distinction ($t = 70.610$, $df = 74$, $p > .05$) between the level of awareness of TERs for teaching, and Teaching Experience since the p-value less the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that there was a significant difference between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources among business education Lecturer in Delta State College of Education,

Table 6: The t-test difference in the frequency of utilization of TERs for Teaching among business education Lecturers in in Delta State Colleges of Education

Variable	Colleges	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p	Decision
Frequency of Utilization of TERs for Teaching	Asaba	45	21.8000	2.85721	73	.486	.628	Not Significant
	Agbor	30	22.1000	2.20266				

Note. SD = standard deviation.

In Table 6, the mean responses for Asaba and Agbor business educators were compared regarding differences in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources (TERs). The results showed that Agbor Business educators had a slightly higher mean response ($M = 22.10$) than Asaba Business educators ($M = 21.80$), with a mean difference of 0.30. However, since both mean scores were not significantly different from the aggregate mean, the responses indicated only slight differences in the frequency of TER utilization for teaching. The table also revealed that there was no notable distinction ($t = .486$, $df = 73$, $p > .05$) between Asaba and Agbor Business educators regarding the utilization of TERs for teaching, as the p-value exceeded the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources among business education Lecturer in Delta State College of Education,

Discussion of Findings

The purpose of the study was to examine the awareness of Business Educators in Delta State Colleges of Education regarding technology-enhanced resources for teaching.

The first research question shows that business educators in Delta States are highly aware of technology-enhanced teaching resources for their academic activities. All seven items on the TERs questionnaire revealed a mean score above the benchmark average, indicating that Business educators have a high level of awareness of TERs for teaching in Delta State. This study is consistent with that of Ementa and Ile (2016), who reported that business educators in tertiary institutions in Southeast Nigeria were aware of Web 2.0 to a high extent. Similarly, this study is in agreement with that of Ubulom and Ogwunte (2017) who opined that business education lecturers in Rivers State tertiary institutions are aware of web-based instructional technology and that they have knowledge of various aspects of web base technology

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The results of the second research question indicate that business educators in Delta States are very frequent in the utilization of TERs in their instructional practice. This finding is in contrast to the report by Liadi, Adedapo, and Ibrahim (2022), which suggests that business educators in tertiary institutions in Edo and Delta States do not use TBIR for their instructional delivery. Furthermore, the study's findings differ from those of Fakomogbon, Olanrewaju, and Soetan (2015), who reported that lecturers use instructional media less frequently.

The findings of the third research question indicate that business educators in Delta States are very frequent in the utilization of TERs in their instructional practice. However, there is no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing technology-enhanced teaching resources among business education lecturers in Delta State College of Education supported by the result of the third hypothesis as shown in Table 6. Similarly, there was a Moderate positive and statistically significant relationship between teaching experience and usage of TER among business educators. Finally, the result of the second hypothesis also revealed that there was a significant difference between the level of awareness of technology-enhanced teaching resources and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Conclusion

The study aimed to investigate the level of awareness and utilization of technology-enhanced resources (TERs) for teaching among Business Educators in Delta State Colleges of Education. The findings revealed that these educators are highly aware of TERs and use them frequently in their instructional practice. Moreover, there was no significant difference in the frequency of utilizing TERs among business education lecturers at Delta State College of Education. The study also found a moderate positive and statistically significant relationship between teaching experience and usage of TERs among business educators. Thus, it can be inferred that there is no distinction in awareness and adoption of TERs between business educators in Delta State. The study concluded that there was a significant difference between the level of awareness of TERs and teaching experience among Business Education lecturers in Colleges of Education in Delta State.

Recommendations

Based on the preceding information and the results of this study, the following recommendations deemed necessary were proffered:

1. Institutional management should allocate resources, provide training, and establish clear expectations of technology integration. This can be achieved by offering targeted professional development through workshops and mentorship programs that can help boost educators' confidence in using technology.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of technology-enhanced teaching, institutional management should establish an ongoing feedback mechanism. This can be accomplished by conducting regular surveys and focus groups with business educators to collect feedback on their experiences.
3. To promote the effective use of technology-enhanced teaching methods, colleges of education should encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing between business educators in Delta States
4. Finally, it is recommended that a digital platform or network be established for ongoing communication and resource sharing between educators. This will further facilitate knowledge sharing and help Business educators stay up to date with the latest technology-enhanced teaching methods.

Acknowledgements.

I want to express my sincere gratitude to the ZIJE Editorial Board at the Faculty of Education for their unwavering support and commitment to fostering scholarly research and disseminating knowledge. Their dedication to excellence and professionalism has been essential in the successful publication of this article. I would also like to express my appreciation to the editorial team and the reviewers for their invaluable feedback and contributions. Thank you very much.

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